

Suddhamāgadhī: The Language of Buddhavacana

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Abstract

Scholars have different opinions about the origin of the Pāli, that we recognize as a language today. Different scholars have tried to make the origination of the word Pāli with different words like- Pariyāya, Pāṭha, Paṅkti, Pāṭali, Palli, Prāleyaka, etc. Similarly, there is a difference of opinion among the scholars regarding the origin-places of the Pāli language. Different scholars consider it as a language of different ancient territories like- Kalinga, Kosala, Ujjayinī, Vindhya-Pradeśa, Magadha, etc. However, from the viewpoint of the literal and regional roots of the Pāli language, the Magadha region seems to be more logical and prominent as origin-place of the Pāli. Thus, Māgadhī is the more appropriate denotement for the Pāli and it is widely accepted by many scholars of Pāli, Buddhology, Linguistics and other allied disciplines.

But there is a big confusion among students, researchers, and scholars somehow associated with linguistics, ancient languages, Buddhist literature, Jaina literature, or Vaidika literature. Although some of them consider Pāli as an independent language, they may not be aware that Pāli could be the modern denotement of the ancient language Māgadhī. On the other hand, many others know this fact, but they become confused with the Māgadhī-Prākṛta.

Thus, through this research paper I have attempted to discuss and introduce both Māgadhī-Pāli and Māgadhī-Prākṛta comparatively and tried to discuss and point-out those features that have established Pāli as an independent language and differentiate it from Prākṛta. And while doing all this, an attempt has been made to discuss whether the word Suddhamāgadhī used by Sri Lankan scholar Sūriyagoḍa Thera for the Māgadhī-Pāli is appropriate or not.

Keywords: Pāli, Māgadhī, Addhamāgadhī, Suddhamāgadhī, Buddhavacana.

Introduction

After attaining enlightenment under the Bodhi-Tree in *Uruvelā*¹ (now Bodha-Gayā, Bihar), Buddha preached the *Dhamma*² for 45 years during his *cārikā*³. The teachings or the Dhamma preached by the Buddha are called *Buddhavacana* (Davids & Stede, 1952, Vol. 6, p. 113). The entire *Buddhavacana* are compiled under these three texts: *Vinaya-Piṭaka*, *Sutta-Piṭaka* and *Abhidhamma-Piṭaka*. These three texts are collectively called *Tipiṭaka*. The language in which *Tipiṭaka* has been compiled is *Pāli*⁴. Later on, many commentaries, sub-commentaries and other texts were also written in Pāli language. On the basis of various literary sources, it can be said that the practice of the word Pāli started from the beginning of the 4th century AD when the word Pāli was used as the discourse of the Buddha in the Sri Lankan chronicle *Dīpavaṃsa*⁵. In some other Buddhist texts also (like- commentaries of *Buddhaghosācariya*⁶, *Mahāvamsa*, *Paramatthadīpanī*, *Culavaṃsa*, *Saddhammasaṅgaha* etc.), the word Pāli represents the *Buddhavacana* or discourse of

¹ A locality on the banks of the Nerañjarā river, in the neighbourhood of the Bodhi-tree at Buddhagayā. Here, after leaving his teachers Aḷāra and Uddaka, the Bodhisatta practised during six years the most severe penances. His companions were the Pañcavaggiya-monks, who, however, left him when he relaxed the severity of his austerities. {Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pali proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 969). London: John Murray.}

² Ācārya Buddhaghosa gives a fourfold meaning of the word Dhamma – (1) guṇe (saddo) : applied to good conduct; (2) desanāyaṃ : to preaching & moral instruction; (3) pariyattiyaṃ : to the nine-fold collection of the Buddha's teachings, Scriptures; (4) nissatte (-nijjivate) : to cosmic (non-animistic) law. {Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pali text society's Pali-English dictionary*. (Vol. 4, p. 171). London: Pali Text Society.}

³ To go on alms-pilgrimage. {Ibid. Vol. 3, p. 95.}

⁴ Literary language of the early Buddhists, closely related to Māgadhī. {Ibid. Vol. 5, p. 78.}

⁵ 'Piṭakattayapāliṃ ca tassā aṭṭhakathāṃ pi ca,
mukhapāṭhena ānesuṃ pubbe bhikkhu mahāmati'.

(Before this time, the wise Bhikkhus had orally handed down the text of the three Piṭakas and also the Aṭṭhakathā.) {Oldenberg, H. (1879). *Dīpavaṃsa*. p. 103. London: Williams and Norgate.}

⁶ The greatest of Commentators on the *Tipiṭaka*. He was a brāhmin, born in a village near Buddhagayā and became proficient in the Vedas and allied branches of knowledge. One day he met a monk, named Revata, and on being defeated by him in controversy, entered the Order to learn the Buddha's teachings. Because his speech was profound, like that of the Buddha, and because his words spread throughout the world (like those of the Buddha), he came to be called Buddhaghosa. {Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pali proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 969). London: John Murray.}

the Buddha (Upādhyāya, 1952, pp. 26-27). But till now the word Pāli was being used not as a language but for entire teachings of the Buddha. The use of the word Pāli as a language begins with the text like *Abhidhānappadīpikā* and *Sāsanavaṃsa*⁷ of the 19th century AD. After that, the term Pāli was being widely used as a language.

Scholars have different opinions about the origin of the Pāli language, that we recognize as a language today. Different scholars have tried to make the origination of the word Pāli with different words like- *Pariyāya*, *Pāṭha*, *Paṃkti*, *Pāṭali*, *Palli*, *Prāleyaka* etc. (Upādhyāya, 1952, pp. 32-33). Similarly, there is a difference of opinion among the scholars regarding the origin-places of the Pāli language. Different scholars consider it as a language of different ancient territories like- *Kaliṅga*, *Kosala*, *Ujjayinī*, *Vindhya-Pradeśa*, *Magadha*, etc. (Upādhyāya, 1952, pp. 40-44). However, from the viewpoint of the literal and regional roots of the Pāli language, the Magadha region seem to be more logical and prominent as origin-place of the Pāli. Thus, *Māgadhī* is the more appropriate denotement for the Pāli and it is widely accepted by different scholars of Pāli, Buddhism, Linguistics and other allied disciplines (Kassapa, 1940, p. 5).

But there is a big confusion among students, researchers and scholars somehow associated or working with linguistics, ancient languages, Buddhist literature, Jaina literature, or Vaidika literature. Although some of them consider Pāli an independent language, they may not be aware that Pāli is the modern denotement of the ancient language Māgadhī. On the other hand, many others know this fact but they become confused with the *Māgadhī-Prākṛta*. And in such a situation, the following questions arise in the mind of most of the people:

1. In ancient time Pāli was known as Māgadhī, so why Pāli is not considered as a dialect of *Prākṛta* language? Is it entirely different from Māgadhī-Prākṛta?
2. If Pāli is different from Māgadhī-Prākṛta, which term would be appropriate to use for it so that it retains the relevance of its antiquity & specialty?

Ācārya *Buddhaghosa*, in his commentaries, considers Māgadhī as *mūlabhāsā*⁸ (principal dialect), in which the Buddha preached his sermons. Buddhaghosa uses the word Pāli to represent

⁷ *Icevaṃ pālibhāsāya pariyattim parivattitvā pacchā ācariyaparamparasissānusissavasena sīhaḍāḍiṇe jinacakkaṃ majjhanti kaṃsumāsī viya atidibbati ...* {Paññāsāmī, Bhikkhu. *Sāsanavaṃsa*. Bode, M. (Ed.). (1897). p. 31. London: The Pāli Text Society. }

⁸ ‘... māgadhikāya sabbasattānaṃ mūlabhāsāya ...’ {Buddhaghosācariya. *Visuddhimagga*. Warren, H.C. (Ed.). (1950). p. 373. Cambridge: Harvard University Press. }

the Buddhavacana or Tipiṭaka⁹. Ācārya *Moggallāna*, at starting of his grammar book, says – “now I am going to tell the rules for Māgadhī dialect”¹⁰. Here *Moggallānācariya* is also talking about the same Māgadhī, which Buddhaghosācariya was talking about. Ācārya *Hemacandra*, in his book *Siddhahemaśabdānuśāsana*, has given many rules for Māgadhī-Prākṛta which are different from the rules of *Māgadhī-Pāli*¹¹. So now, I will discuss both Māgadhī-Prākṛta and Māgadhī-Pāli respectively. But before that we will see the *Thera*¹² Sūriyagoḍa’s perspective about unique identification and recognition of the Māgadhī language in which the Buddhist canons have been preserved and which was used by the Buddha as communicating dialect also. In fact, this was the Thera Sūriyagoḍa’s interpretation that inspired me to write this paper.

Thera *Sūriyagoḍa* of Sri Lanka has used the word *Suddhamāgadhī* to differentiate the Māgadhī of Theravada Buddhist Canon from Māgadhī-Prākṛta. By the term *Suddhamāgadhī* Thera Sūriyagoḍa means the purest form of Māgadhī dialect. However, almost in every religion the language used by its founder or the language of its scriptures is considered the purest. Language of Vedas (*Vaidika Saṃskṛta* or *Chāndasa*) is considered pious. Even at the time of the Buddha, two Brāhmin monks requested the Buddha to make Chāndasa as the primary language of Buddhavacana¹³ but the Buddha refused their proposal by allowing monks to learn or deliver

⁹ ‘... neva pāliyaṃ na atthakathāyaṃ āgataṃ ...’ {Ibid. p. 87}; ‘...neva pāliyaṃ, na atthakathāyaṃ dissati’. {Buddhaghosācariya. *Sumaṅgalavilāsini*. Tiwary, M. (Ed.). (1974). p. 188. Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra. }

¹⁰ “Siddhamiddhaguṇaṃ sādhu, namassitvā tathāgataṃ, sadhammasaṅghaṃ bhāsissaṃ, māgadhaṃ saddalakkhaṇaṃ”.
{Moggallānācārya. *Moggallāna Pāli-vyākaraṇa*. Kausalyāyana, B. A. (Trans.). Vimalakīrti, Prof. (Dr.). (Ed.). (2013). p. 21. New Delhi: Samyaka Prakāśana. }

¹¹ Māgadhī-Pāli is not a technically appropriate term but I am using this term here to differentiate the Māgadhī of Buddhist canons from the Māgadhī-Prākṛta only.

¹² Used with reference to the bhikkhus of Buddhist Order. {Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pali text society's Pali-English dictionary*. (Vol. 4, p. 144). London: Pali Text Society. }

¹³ “Etarahi, bhante, bhikkhū nānānāmā nānāgottā nānājaccā nānākulā pabbajitā. Te sakāya niruttīyā buddhavacanaṃ dūsentī. Handa mayaṃ, bhante, buddhavacanaṃ chandaso āropemā”ti. {*Cullavaggapāli*. Kassapa, J. (Ed.). (2017). (pp. 228-9) Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra. }

Buddhavacana in their own dialects¹⁴. Similarly, Prākṛta, in which the *Mahāvīra Swāmī*¹⁵ preached his discourses, is considered natural & purest language (Pragyāsāgara, 2015, p. IX). Therefore, naming the Pāli language (in which the Buddha delivered his discourses) as *Suddhamāgadhī* may be an attempt to show this language purest and it may be also like showing reverence to the Buddha. But that is neither my concern nor the point of discussion. Purpose of this study is very clear and mainly based upon the two questions which are mentioned in the previous page.

Before proceeding further, it is appropriate to discuss the methodology, significance & scope of this study. Mainly two methods of research have been applied throughout this study – 1. Literary method– the study is based on different relevant primary and secondary literary sources related to Pāli and Prākṛta languages available in printed and electronic form; 2. Analytical method– it has been tried to collect sufficient materials, facts or information related to the topic and has been analyzed to make a critical evaluation of the materials. If we talk about the significance of this study, since the study has been done mainly on account of primary sources, the facts or findings obtained after this study will be more precise and reliable. Researchers and scholars associated with linguistic and historical studies will be attracted to the adequate amount of primary sources available in Pāli and Prākṛta languages. Some popular and controversial questions related to Prākṛta and Pāli language have been considered without any prejudice, so that other future researchers and scholars may also be interested to think over those questions. Future researchers working on similar topics may also be benefited.

It is also necessary to point here that this study is limited to the two grammar texts– *Moggallāna Pāli Vyākaraṇa* and *Siddhahemaśabdānusāsana Prākṛta Vyākaraṇa* to make comparison regarding similarities or differences between the two languages, i.e., Māgadhī (Prākṛta) and *Suddhamāgadhī* (Pāli).

Thera Sūriyagoḍa’s View

At starting of the introduction of his book, Rev. *Sūriyagoḍa Sumaṅgala* admits– “Pāli was the language spoken in the sixth century B.C. in Magadha, a country in Northern India. At that time, it was called Māgadhī and the term Pāli was then unknown. The Buddha, whose teaching

¹⁴ “Na, bhikkhave, buddhavacanaṃ chandaso āropetabbaṃ. Yo āropeyya, āpatti dukkaṭassa. Anujānāmi, bhikkhave, sakāya niruttīyā buddhavacanaṃ pariyāpūṇitu”nti. {Ibid.}

¹⁵ Jainism is believed to have come down from unknown antiquity through 24 teachers, called *Tīrthaṅkaras* (founders of the faith). Rishabha stands first in the list of teachers. However, the first 22 Tirthankaras seem to be mythical and the last two historical persons. 23rd Tīrthaṅkara was Lord Pārśvanātha. Mahāvīra Swāmī was the last and 24th Tīrthaṅkara. {Chanchreek, K.L., & Jain, M.K. (Eds.). (2005). *Encyclopedia of Jaina Religion*. (vol. 1, pp. 64-112). New Delhi: Shree Publishers & Distributors.}

was addressed to all classes of humanity regardless of rank and colour, used this language for His discourses. These discourses have from that day been handed down first orally and later in writing in the same identical language, although the language of the country of Magadha in course of time underwent a great many changes. At first, these changes resulted in a division into three forms –

1. Māgadhī – the language of the court and cultured people,
2. Addhamāgadhī – the language of the merchants and common people and
3. Suddhamāgadhī – the pure Māgadhī which came to be called Pāḷi and which was, as stated above, the language in which the Buddha preached His doctrine and in which the Buddhist Scriptures have been preserved” (Sūriyagoda, 1953, p. 10).

Māgadhī-Prākṛta

Prākṛta is a bunch of languages. There are many dialects of Prākṛta language, and Māgadhī is one of them. However, there is a difference of opinion among scholars, linguists, and grammarians regarding the types of Prākṛta. Where *Vararuci* tells us about four types of Prākṛta, *Lakṣhamīdhara* informs us about six. *Hemacandra* and *Bharatamuni* both mention seven types of Prākṛta. By dividing Prākṛta into four categories (i.e., *Bhāsā*, *Vibhāsā*, *Apabhraṃśa* and *Paiśāca*), *Markaṇḍeya* talks about total sixteen types of Prākṛta¹⁶. But despite having so many types of Prākṛta, only three types of Prākṛta are considered important by most of the scholars – 1. Śaurasenī, 2. Māgadhī and 3. Paiśācī. And among these three, Śaurasenī is considered to be the most important. Māgadhī and Paiśācī are considered to be regional dialects of Śaurasenī only (Pragyāsāgara, 2015, p. X).

Māgadhī is considered the dialect of ancient Magadha. From some famous and important Saṃskṛta plays like *Abhijñānaśākuntalam* of Kālidāsa and *Mṛcchakaṭikam* of Śūdraka, we get to know that Māgadhī was a dialect of common people, King’s men, servants and demon-like characters. Māgadhī can also be traced in Asokan inscriptions. Many ancient Prākṛta scholars have given grammar rules for Māgadhī.

I have selected Ācārya Hemacandra's Siddhahemaśabdānuśāsana for this paper because Ācārya Hemacandra himself has given explanations or comments (*vutti*) to all the suttas written by him. This book is considered as a complete and prominent grammar book of Prākṛta language by many scholars; so this is another reason to select this book for this study. Let us see some examples of Māgadhī from this book.

¹⁶ Hemacandra, Ācārya. *Prākṛta-vyākaraṇa: 8th chapter of Siddhahemaśabdānuśāsana*. Āpte, K. V. (Ed.). (1996). p. 4. Vārāṇasī: Caukhambā Saṃskṛta Series Bhawana.

1. If ‘si’ suffix comes after a masculine noun, the last vowel ‘a’ converts into ‘e’¹⁷ –
 eṣa + si > eśe
 meṣa + si > meśe
 (Note that here ‘ṣ’ also converts into ‘ś’)
2. ‘r’ letter of nouns and adjectives usually converts into ‘l’¹⁸ –
 rājā > lājā
 nara > nale {nara + si = nare; r>l; nare>nale}
 kara > kale
3. Dental ‘s’ & cerebral ‘ṣ’ convert into palatal ‘ś’¹⁹ –
 haṃsa > haṃśe
 sārasa > śālaśe
 puruṣa > पुलिसे
4. ‘ja’ and ‘dya’ convert into ‘ya’²⁰ –
 jānāti > yāñadi
 madya > mayyaṃ
5. ‘t’ (which is non-conjoint and does not occur in starting of a word) converts into ‘d’²¹ –
 jānāti > yāñadi
 upasthita > uvastide
 arthapati > astavadi
 ucchalati > uścaladi

Māgadhī-Pāḷi

Although this is a controversial topic so far and different scholars have different views on this, most scholars agree that Māgadhī was the dialect in which the Buddha preached his sermons.

¹⁷ Ata et sau puṃsi māgadhīyāṃ – “māgadhīyāṃ bhāṣāyāṃ sau pare akārasya ekāro bhavati puṃsi pulliṅge”. {Ibid. p. 242.}

¹⁸ Rasorlaśau – “māgadhīyāṃ refasya dantyasakārasya ca sthāne yathāsaṃkhyāṃ lakārastālavyaśakāraśca bhavati”. {Ibid. pp. 242-243.}

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ Jadyāṃ yaḥ – “māgadhīyāṃ jadyāṃ sthāne yo bhavati. {Ibid. p. 244.}

²¹ To donāḍau śaurasenīyāmayuktasya – “śaurasenīyāṃ bhāṣāyāṃ nānsdāvapadāḍau vartamānasya takārasya dakāro bhavati, na cedasau varṇāntareṇa saṃyukto bhavati. {Ibid. p. 234.}; Seṣaṃ śaurasenīvat – “magdhīyāṃ yaduktāṃ tatonyacchaurasenīvat draṣṭvīyāṃ”. {Ibid. p. 247.}

Later on, this Māgadhī came to be known as Pāli. Scholars such as Ācārya Buddhaghosa, Geiger and Bhikkhu²² Siddhārtha believe that Māgadhī was the language of the Buddhavacana. Bhikkhu Jagadīsa Kassapa also strongly supports this view, as well as many modern scholars of Pāli and Buddhism also have the same view (Upādhyāya, 1952, p. 43).

There are many such problems associated with the Language of Buddhavacana. Even if we assume that Māgadhī was the language of Buddhavacana, then another question arises, which Māgadhī? A variant of Māgadhī is also found in Asokan inscriptions and ancient Saṃskṛta plays, which is different from Māgadhī of Buddhavacana or Pāli in many aspects. We have just seen above a glimpse of Māgadhī used in Asokan inscriptions and ancient Saṃskṛta plays. Now let us see some rules and characteristics of the Māgadhī of Buddhavacana. Then we will come to the conclusion whether it is different from Māgadhī-Prākṛta or not and if it is different, then we should identify or recognise it by a specific denotement or not.

1. If 'si' suffix comes after a masculine noun ending in 'a', this 'a' converts into 'o'²³ –
nara + si > nara
dhamma + si > dhammo
2. 'r' converts into 'l' here also, but this conversion takes place in a very special case when letter 'r' comes after 'pa' –
pari + gha > paligha²⁴
pari + patha > palipatha (Vyāsa, 2019, vol. 2, part. 3, p. 3708)
3. There is only one 's' (dental-s) used in Pāli, palatal 'ś' & cerebral 'ṣ' are not used here (Dhammarakkhita, 1957, p. 3) –
avakāśa > okāsa
kṛṣaka > kassaka
4. In Māgadhī-Pāli 'dya' usually converts into 'jja' –
vidyā > vijjā
madya > majja

²² An almsman, a mendicant, a Buddhist monk or priest. {Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pali text society's Pali-English dictionary*. (Vol. 6, p. 128). London: Pali Text Society. }

²³ Sisso – "akārantato nāmasmā sissa o hoti". {*Moggallāna, Ācārya. Moggallāna Pāli-vyākaraṇa*. Kausalyāyana, B. A. (Trans.). Vimalakīrti, Prof. (Dr.). (Ed.). (2013). p. 82. New Delhi: Samyaka Prakāśana. }

²⁴ Tathānarānaṃ taṭhaṇalā – "tathānarānaṃ taṭhaṇalā honti vā". {Ibid. p. 36. }

5. Here ‘*t*’ sometimes converts into ‘*ṭ*’ but not usually into ‘*d*’²⁵ –
dukkaṭaṃ > dukkaṭaṃ
atthakathā > aṭṭhakathā

Conclusion

As we have observed above, there are differences between Māgadhī-Prākṛta and Māgadhī-Pāḷi. In Māgadhī-Prākṛta, there are more vowels and consonants than Māgadhī-Pāḷi which make this dialect more complex and somehow of hybridized nature. Tendencies like – changing *r* into *l*, *s* & *ṣ* into *ś*, *ja* & *dya* into *ya*, *ta* into *da*, last vowel ‘*a*’ (of nominative singular noun) into ‘*e*’ – can be seen usually in Māgadhī-Prākṛta but these characteristics are generally not found in Māgadhī-Pāḷi, even if found anywhere, it is a very rare case. Thus, ***Suddhamāgadhī*** is an appropriate and relevant nomenclature for the Māgadhī language of Buddhist canon from the perspective of both perspicuity and disparity from Māgadhī-Prākṛta.

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²⁵ ibid.

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